

DEPARTMENTALIZATION IN THE ELEMENTARY SCHOOL CLASSROOMS FOR AN IMPROVED QUALITY OF INSTRUCTION: BASIS FOR SCHOOL ADMINISTRATION AND SUPERVISION

GLAIZA B. LAYA

glaiza.laya@deped.gov.ph

Laguna State Polytechnic University, San Pablo City, Laguna, Philippines

ABSTRACT

The study attempted to determine the correlation of quality of instruction to the departmentalized setting in the classroom in elementary schools. The study utilized inferential type of research was used and applied an adapted and modified questionnaires served as the main tool in gathering needed information that consists of three parts, profile of the respondents, perception of the teacher on departmentalize setting in the classroom, and quality instruction. Majority of the respondents are female and married. Most of them bachelors degree with masteral units. The distribution of the respondents has a small amount of difference and mostly Teacher I. Majority of the respondents were agreed that Departmentalize setting in the classroom of the teacher affect the equality of instruction. The result reveals that departmentalize setting in the classroom are significantly related to and quality of instruction.

Keywords: departmentalize, inferential type of research, adapted and modified questionnaires, equality